

We report here the isolation and characterisation of a rare flavonol diglycoside lepidoside (1) along with kaempferitrin (2), free kaempferol (3) and crosemperine. This is a second report of isolation of lepidoside (1), obtained previously from *Lepidium perfoliatum* (Cruciferae)³, while kaempferitrin has been isolated previously from a number of plant species^{4,5}. Co-occurrence of 1 and 2 has not however been known so far.

The n-BuOH-soluble fraction of the alcoholic extract on solvent fractionation followed by column chromatography of the methanol-soluble fraction yielded compounds 1 and 2. Compound 1 on acid hydrolysis yielded kaempferol (3), while L-rhamnose and D-xylose were detected in the aqueous hydrolysate. Compound 1 showed $\lambda_{\max}(\text{MeOH})$ 263 and 346 nm, which on adding AlCl_3 showed a bathochromatic shift of band-I by 52 nm that did not change on addition of HCl. This suggested that C-5 hydroxyl was free while C-3 hydroxyl was substituted⁶. This was further evident from negative Zirconium citrate test⁷. Moreover, there was no shift in the uv spectrum of 1 on addition of sodium acetate, suggesting that C-7 hydroxyl was also substituted⁶. It was thus evident that the sugars are linked through C-3 and C-7 hydroxyl groups of kaempferol (3). Compound 1 gave an octaacetate on acetylation with pyridine and Ac_2O .

The selective hydrolysis⁸ of 1 with 0.5% aqueous KOH yielded 7-O- α -L-rhamnosylkaempferol, while D-xylose was identified by pc in the aqueous hydrolysate. This fully supported the structure of 1 as 3-D-xylosyl-7- α -rhamnosylkaempferol known as lepidoside.

- 1 ; R¹=D-xylose, R²=L-rhamnose
 2 ; R¹=R²=L-rhamnose
 3 ; R¹=R²=H

Lepidoside—A Rare Flavonol Diglycoside from *Crotalaria semperflorens* Vent.†

HIRESH DHASMANA and H. S. GARG*

Medicinal Chemistry Division,
 Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow-226 001

Manuscript received 30 July 1990, accepted 31 July 1991

A pyrrolizidine alkaloid, crosemperine has been reported from the seeds of *Crotalaria semperflorens* Vent.¹. No other work appears to have been carried out on this plant. The alcoholic extract of the aerial part of the plant showed antiviral activity² against Ranikhet disease virus and was taken up for detailed chemical investigation. The antiviral activity was found to be localised in the n-butanol soluble fraction of the crude ethanolic extractive.

† CDRI Communication no. 4729.

None of the isolated compounds however showed antiviral activity.

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Acculab-1 spectrophotometer, uv spectra (MeOH) on a Hitachi 320 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) instrument using TMS as internal reference.

The plant material was collected from Snowdon area in Tamil Nadu state, during flowering and fruiting season in November by the Botany Division

of the Institute (a voucher specimen is preserved in the herbarium of the Institute).

Extraction and isolation: Air-dried powdered aerial parts (13 kg) of *C. semperflorens* was extracted with 80% alcohol ($4 \times 15 \text{ dm}^3$). The total alcohol extract was concentrated under reduced pressure at $< 60^\circ$ and the concentrate was fractionated into hexane, CHCl_3 , butanol and water soluble fractions. A part of n-butanol-soluble fraction, on acid extraction (5% aqueous HCl) yielded crosemperine, while another part (10 g) was triturated with ethyl acetate, acetone and methanol successively to yield ethyl acetate-soluble (1.5 g), acetone-soluble (2.0 g) and methanol-soluble (5.0 g) fractions.

The methanol-soluble fraction was dissolved in dry methanol (50 ml) and precipitated with solvent ether (400 ml). The process was repeated twice to give a mixture of flavonol glycosides Gl (3.0 g). The semi-purified glycoside Gl was chromatographed over silica gel (100 g) using EtOAc–MeOH gradient as eluent collecting 200 ml fractions each. On elution with EtOAc–MeOH (5 : 1), fractions 34–55 afforded kaempferitrin (2 ; 300 mg) while lepidoside (1 ; 150 mg) was obtained from fractions 56–65.

Lepidoside (1): Repeated crystallisation with acetone-methanol (4 : 1) of the above fractions 56–65 yielded lepidoside (1) as yellow crystals, m.p. $240-45^\circ$ (lit.³ $260-65^\circ$); R_f 0.83 (n-BuOH–AcOH– H_2O , 4 : 1 : 1); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 400, 2 920, 1 650, 1 580, 1 450, 1 050, 970 and 850 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (MeOH) 263, 315sh and 346 nm, (+ AlCl_3) 275, 300sh, 345sh and 398 nm, (+ AlCl_3 +HCl) no further change, (NaOAc) 263, 315sh and 340sh nm, (NaOH) 270, 280sh and 390 nm; δ (CDCl_3 + CD_3OD) 7.70 (2H, d, J 9 Hz, 2',6'-H), 6.90 (2H, d, J 9 Hz, 3',5'-H), 6.62 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, 8-H), 6.40 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, 6-H), 5.50 (1H, bs), 5.40 (1H, bs, ArH of the sugar moieties), 1.16 (3H, d, J 6 Hz, CH_3 of rhamnose unit) and 3.2–4.0 (9H, sugar protons).

Acid hydrolysis of 1 to kaempferol: Lepidoside (1 ; 50 mg) in methanol (5 ml) was refluxed on water-bath with 2% aqueous H_2SO_4 (2 ml) for 30 min and processed to yield kaempferol, m.p. $273-74^\circ$, m.m.p. $273-74^\circ$, and the sugars in the aqueous hydrolysate on paper co-chromatography (n-BuOH saturated with water) showed two spots corresponding to L-rhamnose and D-xylose.

Acetylation of lepidoside (1): 1 (60 mg) in pyridine (0.5 ml) and acetic anhydride (1.0 ml) was left overnight at room temperature, then poured over crushed ice, and the precipitated acetate was washed, dried and crystallised from methanol to yield a dirty white powder, m.p. $140-45^\circ$; R_f 0.2 (CHCl_3 –MeOH, 18 : 2); ν_{max} (KBr) 2 920, 1 750, 1 650, 1 370, 1 220, 1 050 and 960 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (MeOH) 250 and 300 nm; δ 7.80 (2H, d, J 9 Hz, 2',6'-H), 7.20 (2H, d, J 9 Hz, 3',5'-H), 7.0 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, 8-H), 6.70 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, 6-H), 5.50 (1H, bs), 5.40 (1H, bs, ArH of sugar moieties), 2.38 (3H, s, C-5 OCOCH_3), 2.28 (3H, s, C-4' OCOCH_3), 2.10–1.90 (18H, $6 \times \text{OCOCH}_3$), 1.17 (3H, d, J 6 Hz, rhamnosyl CH_3) and 3.4–4.6 (remaining sugar protons).

Selective hydrolysis of 1: Lepidoside (1 ; 10 mg) in MeOH (2 ml) was refluxed⁸ with 0.5% aqueous KOH (1 ml) for 10–12 min over a water-bath. The reaction mixture was neutralised with aqueous HCl (2%) in cold, methanol was then removed, the solution diluted with water and extracted with ethyl acetate. The aqueous hydrolysate on paper co-chromatography showed one spot corresponding to D-xylose and the partially hydrolysed glycoside was identified as 7-O- α -L-rhamnosylkaempferol, m.p. $220-25^\circ$ (lit.⁹ $226-28^\circ$); λ_{max} (MeOH) 223, 265, 318sh and 359 nm, (+ AlCl_3) 223, 270, 345sh and 418 nm, (+ AlCl_3 +HCl) same as with AlCl_3 , (+NaOAc) 224, 266, 317sh and 360 nm.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the staff of R.S.I.C. for spectral data and to Dr. D. S. Bhakuni, Head, Medicinal Chemistry Division, for his interest in this work. One of the authors (H.D.) is grateful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

References

1. C. K. ATAL, C. C. J. CULVENOR, R. S. SAWHNEY and L. W. SMITH, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1967, **20**, 805.
2. Z. ABRAHAM, D. S. BHAKUNI, H. S. GARG, A. K. GOEL, B. N. MEHROTRA and G. K. PATNAIK, *Indian J. Exp Biol.*, 1986, **24**, 48.
3. N. S. FURSA and V. I. LITVINENKO, *Chem Abstr.*, 1970, **73**, 99156.
4. M-Tin. Wa, N. R. FARNSWORTH and H. H. S. FONG, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1969, **32**, 509 and references cited therein; J. B. HARBORNE, T. J. MABRY and H. MABRY, "The Flavonoids", Academic, New York, 1975, p. 415.
5. K. L. EULER and M. ALAM, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1982, **45**, 220 and references cited therein.
6. T. J. MABRY, K. R. MARKHAM and M. B. THOMAS, "The Systematic Identification of Flavonoids", Springer-Verlag, New York, 1970, p. 35.
7. K. MEHRA, Ph. D. Thesis, Allahabad University, 1975; N. V. SERGEEVA, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1963, **59**, 10473.
8. J. B. HARBORNE, T. J. MABRY and H. MABRY, "The Flavonoids", Academic, New York, 1975, p. 387.
9. R. B. HALINA, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1970, **73**, 22154.